

=====
**Artificial Intelligence (AI) Assistance in Improving
the Literacy of Grade 9 Learners**
=====

Allan De La Torre

La Consolacion College, Bacolod City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8742-9913> | allandelatorre@gmail.com

Edson A. Macapagong

College Instructor, Monkayo College of Arts, Sciences, and Technology, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9862-5975> | edsonahum@gmail.com

Jaycee Pieri S. Magbanua

Secondary Mathematics Teacher, Department of Education, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-2788-6040> | vermont.sphinx@gmail.com

Hazel M. Lim

TIC-Values Education, Department of Education, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-5500-9961> | hazel.lim@deped.gov.ph

Jearly Gift B. Ortiz

Elementary Teacher, Department of Education, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-1577-9203> | jearlygift.ortiz@deped.gov.ph

Abstract

Acquiring proficient literacy skills is a crucial milestone in a student's educational journey, significantly influencing their academic success and intellectual development. This study explores the potential of integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a tool to enhance literacy proficiency among Grade 9 learners. Introducing AI-driven Text-to-Speech (TTS) technology as a teaching aid for grade 9 learners is an exciting venture into the future of education. AI-powered TTS offers a remarkable tool that transcends traditional learning boundaries, empowering students with auditory learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles. This technology harnesses the power of artificial intelligence to convert written text into spoken words, creating an immersive and engaging learning environment. By leveraging TTS, educators can enhance comprehension, language skills, and accessibility for all students, fostering a more inclusive and dynamic classroom. We gathered quantitative data to evaluate the impact of AI-assisted intervention in teaching English focusing on comprehension. The findings indicate substantial enhancements in literacy skills, highlighting the promise of AI as a valuable resource in modern education

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, text-to-speech (TTS) literacy skills, Grade 9 learners, educational technology, intervention

Introduction

UNESCO's Global Education Monitoring Report 2023 highlights that the arrival of AI content-generating tools like ChatGPT and intelligent tutorials proved invaluable in providing personalized support for students, particularly those with disabilities or living in remote areas

The Philippine Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) launched the National AI Roadmap in the year 2021, aiming to identify opportunities and challenges that AI presents to Philippine industries by 2024. It involves four (4) important dimensions to determine our readiness for AI which include (1) digitalization and infrastructure, (2) research and development, (3) Workforce Development, and (4) tasks. -Estrellado (2023) There are some benefits to using artificial intelligence, as time is something most teachers don't have. One of the challenges encountered by most educators is the reviewing and checking of students' work

The study of Mark Anthony Llego (2023), states that with the help of AI, it can automate administrative tasks, such as managing student records, scheduling, monitoring attendance, and evaluating student's progress. AI tools can

help facilitate more efficient communication between educators, parents, and students, providing real-time updates on school events and student performance.

The indicated were in the premise as education goals found in the Basic Education Development Program (BEDP) 2030 program of the Department of Education (DepEd) which will be used as predictive models, making AI to facilitate decision-making in schools by providing insights and recommendations based on collected data, helping institutions make more informed decisions regarding resource allocation, curriculum development, and student support programs. The government of the Philippines has recognized the potential of Artificial Intelligence in various industries, education included.

In today's changing world, we're seeing technology, like artificial intelligence (AI), making its way into education. One exciting area where AI is making a difference is in helping people learn to read and write better. This study takes a closer look at how AI tools can impact the way we learn literacy skills, such as reading and language development, and how it might change the way we teach and learn.

For a long time, we've been using traditional methods to teach literacy, but these methods can sometimes be limited, especially when it comes to meeting the individual needs of each student. Now, with the help of AI as assistance in literacy learning, we have a chance to create more personalized learning experiences. AI uses smart algorithms and technology to adapt to each person's unique learning style, potentially making a big difference in how we improve our reading and writing skills.

As we explore this topic, we want to understand not only how AI as assistance in literacy learning works but also how it fits into our existing ways of teaching and learning. We'll look at the good things it brings, the challenges it might contribute to literacy learning, and what it means for education in the future. By doing this study, we hope to share insights that can help teachers, decision-makers, and researchers understand the role of AI in shaping the way we learn and teach literacy.

The researchers use the term "AI" which according to Sam Thompson in his article *AI in Education-All you need to know*, (2023) refers to the use of artificial intelligence or "computers" mimicking human perception and decision-making to complete a task in the classroom. Like analyzing and grading, plagiarism detection, and suggesting specific learning paths based on assessment results or students' interests.

Artificial Intelligence is a human intelligence simulation based on computers and networks and is designed to function as human beings. AI is one of the drivers of the 4.0 industrial revolution to facilitate education in teaching and learning (Fitria, 2021). Additionally, in essence, AI-driven Text-to-Speech (TTS) aligns with the Industrial Revolution's principles of accessibility, efficiency, and innovation. By leveraging this technology, education can evolve to meet the demands of a rapidly changing world, preparing learners to thrive in the dynamic industrial landscape of the future.

The acquisition of strong literacy skills is a pivotal aspect of a student's educational journey, influencing academic success and cognitive development. In recent years, the integration of technology, particularly Artificial Intelligence (AI), has emerged as a promising avenue for enhancing educational outcomes across various domains. This study centers on the application of AI as assistance in literacy learning in the context of improving the literacy skills of Grade 9 learners.

By incorporating TTS technology into the teaching environment, non-native English-speaking teachers can bridge language gaps, enhance the quality of language instruction, and provide students with a more comprehensive and standardized learning experience in the English language. Assuming a progressive cost-reduction to produce publishable subtitles in diverse target languages, it is also natural to consider the use of text-to-speech (TTS) tools to efficiently dub the lecturer's speech in target languages she/he might not even speak (Perez, et.al., 2021).

This study is prompted by a notable increase in frustrated learners, as reported by the Department of Education (DepEd) and emphasized by Cristina Chi of Philstar. This is due to the pandemic disruption of classes and reflected in the results of the national reading program conducted recently.

Objectives of the Study

This study seeks to specifically answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of literacy skills of Grade 9 learners before and after AI intervention?

2. Is there a significant difference in the level of literacy skills of grade 9 learners before and after intervention?

Hypotheses

Based on the aforementioned problems, the following hypothesis is advanced:

1. There is no significant difference in the level of literacy skills of grade 9 learners before and after intervention.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study used a descriptive type of research. It aims to gather information about the phenomenon concerning Artificial Intelligence (AI) assistance in improving the literacy of grade 9 learners during the school year 2023-2024. The descriptive type of research is a fact-finding procedure that is concerned with the condition that exists, practices that prevail, attitudes, beliefs, or points of view that are held, processes that are going on, or trends that are developing such as the case of this investigation (Aquino, 2005 as cited by Hojilla, 2022).

Respondents of the Study

This study used a descriptive type of research. It aims to gather information about the phenomenon concerning Artificial Intelligence (AI) in improving the literacy of grade 9 learners during the school year 2023-2024. The descriptive type of research is a fact-finding procedure that is concerned with the condition that exists, practices that prevail, attitudes, beliefs, or points of view that are held, processes that are going on, or trends that are developing such as the case of investigation. (Aquino, 2005, as cited by Hojilla, 2022)

Data Gathering Instrument

This study aims to investigate the improvement of performance among Grade 9 students at Old Sagay National High School through AI assistance. The research instrument is a researcher-made structured questionnaire composed of 20 test items designed to collect data from a sample of 70 Grade 9 students. The test questionnaires were adopted from the competencies of English Nine Most Essential Learning Competencies for the second quarter.

Validity

Since the instrument is researcher-made, it has undergone a validity test by a jury panel composed of 3 experts in the fields of education and research. They evaluated and validated the test items of the instrument using Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio (CVR). They have found the 20 items essential which means that the instrument is valid to be administered.

Reliability

To establish the reliability of this research instrument, the questionnaire was administered to 70 grade 9 high school students of Old Sagay National High School. the result of the test was correlated employing Chronbach Alpha and the result revealed a value of 0.973. thus, the reliability of the instrument was excellent.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following steps have been observed before the gathering of data:

- a. A communication that seeks permission to conduct the study has been sent to the principal of Old Sagay National High School.
- b. The list of grade 9 students who fall in the frustration level of Phil-IRI results has been gathered from the respective class advisers.
- c. The parental consent of the 70 participants has been secured through a parent's orientation which explained the main purpose of the study.
- d. The refinement of the research instrument through a validity and reliability test.
- e. The researchers administered the test instruments to the respondents through Pre and Post-Tests in a week's interval.

The AI "text-to-speech" incorporated in the actual classroom instruction wherein the discussion proper textual part was converted to AI. The AI voice was the one that spoke while the covered parts of the texts were simultaneously highlighted.

Ethical Considerations

In crafting quantitative research exploring Artificial Intelligence (AI) in assisting in improvements of students' literacy, ethical considerations need to be met in shaping the study's integrity. And safeguarding the well-being of participants. Informed consent from both students and their parents or guardians was obtained first. Clear communication about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks ensured that participants made voluntary decisions in the research. Privacy and confidentiality were paramount ethical principles, particularly in a study involving students.

The researchers implemented robust measures to protect participants' identities and sensitive information. Addressing the respondents' population as a whole and securing data storage practices helped maintain the anonymity of individuals involved, fostering trust and confidence in the research process. Equity and fairness are ethical imperatives, especially when considering the potential impact of AI interventions on literacy improvement.

The researchers were mindful of diverse cultural, social, and economic backgrounds among Grade 9 learners, ensuring that the benefits and burdens of participation were distributed fairly. This commitment to fairness not only aligned with ethical standards but also contributed to the overall validity and applicability of the research findings.

Continuous monitoring throughout the research process is essential for identifying and addressing any unforeseen ethical issues promptly. Regular check-ins with participants, coupled with the opportunity for debriefing at the study's conclusion, facilitate an open dialogue to address issues.

Results and Discussion

To determine the level of literacy improvement of Grade 9 learners before and after AI intervention, a mean was applied. The 20-item test has been dispersed into the following scale:

Score Range	Interpretation
1-7.33	Low
7.34-13.67	Average
13.68-20	High

The scores revealed that during the pretest the mean score was at 6.6714 (Low) and during the post-test, it proved to be 12.7143 (Average).

To determine the difference in the level of literacy improvement of grade 9 learners before and after the intervention, a paired t-test was used. It resulted in a mean of 6.04286 with a correlation of 0.324 thus, interpreted as average.

The data was tallied and tabulated with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the positive impact of AI assistance in enhancing the literacy skills of Grade 9 learners. From 6.6714 (Low) to 12.7143 (Average) mean values in the test results are a significant indicator of this improvement. The findings emphasize the value of integrating AI-TTS in English instruction, particularly in enhancing comprehension during the discussion proper.

It indicates that the employment of AI-TTS in instruction can indeed help increase the level of literacy of the learners. Other factors can further influence the post-test results like attention, discipline, and ventilation.

They observed improvements in literacy skills underscore the potential of AI-assisted interventions in modern education. The personalized learning experiences and standardized language support offered by AI systems address the diverse learning needs of students, particularly at the pivotal grade 9 level.

The acceptability of the study is both necessary for students and teachers to improve literacy in English. The study proves that AI Assistance has a very significant impact in improving the literacy level of the Grade 9 students of OSNHS. The AI assistance in improving the literacy of Grade 9 Learners is beneficial for teachers especially in reading since AI can pronounce the words correctly and it also lessens the work of the teacher by providing a text-to-speech algorithm that could be useful in assisting students with special needs such as dyslexic students, the deaf, the mute as well as the blind.

According to Paid (2023) in his article "Filipinos open to learning more about AI", some 55 percent of the respondents said they were already using AI in their jobs while 47 percent said trying out ChatGPT, a chatbot that

is language model-based that can generate human-like text. Teachers and students alike have been into AI unconsciously. It has evolved over the years and has taken a wider leap when the pandemic arrived. Schools and institutions have devised ways to communicate remotely and continue their operations through the aid of available technological applications.

Rodrigo (2023) also stated that AI in Education has positive effects on student achievement in general and is particularly effective at helping low achievers. The bad news is that many factors inhibit the Philippines from using AI to address our educational ills. It requires computers. Despite the Computerization Program, there are still reported schools with no available computer units for teachers and students. Teachers have to strategize and find ways to augment learning despite of absence of these facilities.

As a mode of adaptation to the 21st-century classroom setting, AI-assisted instruction will benefit the teachers in conducting their classes, and it helps in improving learner's literacy. Assessment in the 21st-century classroom should focus on evaluating content knowledge and 21st-century skills. Traditional assessment forms such as tests, quizzes, and exams still exist nowadays. But with the aid of new assessment modes, including portfolios, performance tasks, project-based assessments, peer assessments, and the introduction of AI assistance, the teaching delivery of the teachers becomes more efficient.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion made by the researchers, the following recommendations are given:

- a. Students may use AI Assistance to cope with their studies. Learners with special needs may also read or listen to recorded passages.
- b. Teachers may use AI assistance to improve the delivery of the lesson during discussion and capture and sustain the attention of students for better learning engagement.
- c. Administrators may adopt AI assistance as one of the innovations of the school and could be included in the school improvement plan.
- d. Future Researchers can widen the scope of study and explore other AI software available that could potentially improve the teaching and learning process.

References

Baker, Ethan (2023, February 16). AI Evolution: The Future of Text-To-Speech Synthesis. Retrieved from <https://www.veritonevoice.com/blog/future-of-text-to-speech-synthesis.text=AI%20text%2Dto%2Dspeech%20is.speech%20outputs%20from%20the%20text:~#:/>

Chi, Cristina (2023, April 3) - "New report shows the drastic economic impact of illiteracy on the Philippines". Philstar.com. Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/04/03/2256606/new-report-shows-dramatic-economic-impact-illiteracy-Philippines>

Crossman, Ashley (2019) Reliability- Definition of Reliability in Research (thoughtco.com)

Estrellado, Carie Justine (2023, May 5). "Artificial Intelligence in the Philippine Educational Context: Circumspection and Future Inquiries". International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 13, Issue 5. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370603250_Artificial_Intelligence_in_the_Philippine_Educational_Context_Circumspection_and_Future_Inquiries

Fitria, T. N. (2021). The Use of Technology Based on Artificial Intelligence in English Teaching and Learning. ELT Echo: The Journal of English Language Teaching in Foreign Language Context, 6(2), 213-223

Frost, Jim (2023) Cronbach's alpha- Cronbach's Alpha: Definition, Calculations & Example - Statistics By Jim. <https://courier.unesco.org/en/articles/education-age-artificial-intelligence>

Heath (2023, February 5). What is purposive sampling? Retrieved from <https://dovetail.com/research/purposive-sampling>

Llego, Mark Anthony (2023). How to Survive the AI Revolution: A Human-Centered Approach to AI in Philippine Education - TeacherPH. Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/surviving-ai>

Introduction to SAS. UCLA: Statistical Consulting Group. from <https://stats.oarc.ucla.edu/sites/modules/introduction-to-the-features-of-SAS> The Importance of Technology in Philippine Education (2021, March 15). Retrieved from [/https://childhope.org.ph/importance-of-technology-in-philippine-education](https://childhope.org.ph/importance-of-technology-in-philippine-education)

Maguate, G., Sotto, N. A., Moises, R., Ohoylan, J. G., & Alegre, A. (2024). Efficacy of National Learning Camp to Literacy and Numeracy of Grade 7 Learners. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence*, 1(1),68-72.

..Pérez, A., Díaz-Munío, G. G., Giménez, A., Silvestre-Cerdà, J. A., Sanchis, A., Civera, J Juan, A. (2021). Towards cross-lingual voice cloning in higher education. *Engineering & Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 105, 104413

Paid, Tyrone Jasper (2023, September 15) Filipinos are open to learning more about AI, a LinkedIn study shows. Retrieved from <https://business.inquirer.net/421134/filipinos-open-to-learning-more-about-ai-says-linkedin-study>

Rodrigo, Maria Mercedes T. (2023, July 28) The Truth About using AI in schools. Retrieved from <https://philstarlife.com/news-and-views/283288-truth-about-using-ai-schools?page=4>

Rosala, Maria; Moran, Kate (2022, July 24) The Funnel Technique in Qualitative Research. Retrieved from <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/the-funnel-technique-in-qualitative-user-research>

Thompson, Sam (2022, March 23) AI In Education - All You Need to Know | Kaltura, AI In Education – All You Need to Know from <https://corp.kaltura.com/blog/ai-in-education>